

The Protective Action of Soaps and Further Evidence in favour of the Chemical Theory of Adsorption.

Part III

By

S. S. BHATNAGAR, MATA PRASAD AND D. C. BAHL.

Zsigmondy (The Chemistry of Colloids, p. 112, 1917), has found that when gelatine is adsorbed by a thin foil of gold, it loses the property of solution in hot water. He, therefore, concludes that the protective action of soaps cannot be satisfactorily explained by simple thermodynamical reasoning. He believes that some chemical forces play an important part in the process of adsorption.

Bhatnagar and Srivastava (Journ. Phys. Chem., 28, 730, 1924) have studied the protection of sols and fine precipitates by sugars. They found that the optical rotation of a mixture of sugar solution and sol was not the same as expected on Beer's Law but was less. They have postulated that the decrease in rotation is due to the adsorption of sugar by the colloidal particles and that the adsorbed sugar loses the property of rotating the plane of polarisation. By simple combustion experiments they have shown that the constituents of sugars are present in the coagula but they observed no optical rotation in solutions obtained by dissolving these coagula in proper solvents. These results have further been confirmed in a paper by Shrivastava, Gupta, Prasad and Bhatnagar (Journ. Phys. Chem., Feb. 1925). It has been definitely shown there that the optical inactivity of solutions of

coagula containing adsorbed sugar is not due to any other cause such as mutarotation but is due to a change in the nature of the sugar itself.

It becomes, therefore, interesting to see whether the observations of Zsigmondy and Bhatnagar and Shrivastava were peculiar to gelatine and sugars only or had a general application. In order, therefore, to obtain further evidence on the chemical theory of adsorption, the protection of colloidal solutions by soap solution was studied and the nature of adsorbed soap particles was in all cases examined.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The colloidal solutions used in the investigations were those of Arsenic hydrosulphide, Antimony hydrosulphide and Cadmium hydrosulphide. The colloidal solutions of Arsenic and Antimony hydrosulphides were prepared by dissolving Merck's pure Arsenious acid and Potassium Antimony tartrate, respectively, in freshly twice distilled water and then passing Hydrogen sulphide gas for some time. The excess of the gas was removed by passing a rapid current of Hydrogen gas through the solutions for about 24 hours until a sample of the sol produced no stain on lead acetate paper. The colloidal solution of Cadmium hydrosulphide was prepared by passing Hydrogen sulphide gas in an ammoniacal solution of Merck's pure Cadmium sulphate whereby Cadmium sulphide was precipitated. The precipitate was well washed on the filter paper until it was quite free from Ammonium Sulphate. It was then suspended in twice distilled water and Hydrogen sulphide gas was passed in, till a clear solution was obtained. The excess of the gas was removed by boiling the solution.

The soap solution, used, was that of Sodium oleate, which was prepared in the laboratory by the method

advocated by McBain. Alcoholic solution of Sodium hydroxide was added gradually to an alcoholic solution of Oleic acid and the neutrality of the mixture was tested by Phenolphthalein. The soap was then dried till it was completely free from alcohol. The sample thus prepared had a melting point 232° - 235° .

A solution of Sodium oleate was prepared by dissolving 5 grams of the soap in a litre of distilled water and solutions of other concentrations were obtained by diluting the original solution with water in varying proportions.

The investigation was accomplished by the use of Donnan's Drop pipette (*Zeits. Phys. Chem.*, *31*, 42, 1899) by means of which the number of drops in a given volume of the solution of soap were counted under standard conditions. The method of Drop numbers has been employed by Donnan and Potts (*Koll. Zeit.*, *4*, 208, 1910) in determining the emulsifying powers of alkalis. Lewis (*Phil. Mag.* 499, 1908) also used the same method in the study of adsorption of Sodium Glycolate by the oil surface for the verification of the Gibbs-Thomson equation.

As the number of drops are greatly affected by the irregularities in the tip of the drop-pipette, it was carefully smoothed and necessary precautions were taken to keep it protected from grease or dust particles. The drop-pipette was cleaned with Potassium dichromate mixture and distilled water and was well dried before each observation

The number of drops in a fixed volume of solutions of soaps of various concentrations were first counted. A curve was then drawn with the concentration of soap solution as abscissa and the number of drops as ordinates as shown in Figure I. The variation in drop number with

change in concentration of soap solution is brought out in the following table.

TABLE I.

No.	Concentration of soap solution.	Drop number.
1	0.0000%	240
2	0.0625%	568
3	0.1250%	617
4	0.1875%	624
5	0.2500%	631
6	0.3125%	638
7	0.3750%	645
8	0.4375%	652
9	0.5000%	659

It will be seen from the above table that Drop numbers increase with increase in concentration of the soap. As drop numbers are inversely proportional to surface tension as a first approximation, it shows that the surface tension of soap solutions continuously decreases as the concentration of the soap is increased.

The Drop numbers of the various colloidal solutions employed in the investigation were counted in the same volume as that of soap solutions and the results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II.

No.	Sols.	Drop number.
1	Arsenic Hydrosulphide	240
2	Antimony Hydrosulphide.	240
3	Cadmium Hydrosulphide.	240

The above table clearly shows that the colloidal particles do not take any part in altering the surface tension of the dispersing medium as the drop numbers for the three colloidal solutions examined are exactly the same as that of water (*cf.* Linder and Picton; Journ. Chem. Soc. 61, 114, 1892). This property of colloidal solution greatly facilitated the work as the addition of the colloidal solution to soap solution produced a simple dilution effect and the concentration of soap before adsorption could be easily calculated.

25 C. C. of the colloidal solutions were mixed with 25 C. C. of the soap solutions of different concentrations and were left for 24 hours. The number of drops in the same volume of the mixed solutions were then counted and the concentrations of the soap after adsorption were read off from the graph. The amount of soap adsorbed per 100 C.C. of the sol was then calculated and the values of x/m were obtained. The results of the investigation are shown in the following tables:—

TABLE III.

Soap used = Sodium oleate.
 Colloidal substance used = Arsenic hydrosulphide sol containing 0.8530 gram of AS_2S_3 per litre.

Original concentration of soap solution before mixing the sol.	Calculated concentration of soap in the mixed solution before adsorption.	Drop number of the mixture of sol and soap solution	Observed concentration of soap in the mixed solution after adsorption.	Amount of soap adsorbed per 100 C.C. of the sol.	x/m
0.5000%	0.2500%	595	0.0688%	0.3624 gms.	4.249
0.3750%	0.1875%	518	0.0500%	0.2750 "	3.224
0.2500%	0.1250%	371	0.0250%	0.2000 "	2.345
0.1250%	0.0625%	268	0.0068%	0.1124 "	1.317

TABLE IV.

Soap used = Sodium oleate.
 Colloidal substance used = Antimony hydrosulphide
 sol containing 0.3530
 gram of Sb_2S_3 per litre.

Original concentration of soap solution before mixing the sol.	Calculated concentration of soap in the mixed solution before adsorption.	Drop number of the mixture of sol and soap solution.	Observed concentration of soap in the mixed solution after adsorption.	Amount of soap adsorbed per 100 C.C. of the sol.	x/m
0.5000%	0.2500%	617	0.1250%	0.2500 gms	7.081
0.3750%	0.1875%	608	0.0875%	0.2000 "	5.665
0.2500%	0.1250%	588	0.0656%	0.1188 "	3.366
0.1250%	0.0625%	365	0.0250%	0.0750 "	0.212

TABLE V.

Soap used = Sodium oleate.
 Colloidal substance used = Cadmium sulphide hydro-
 sol.

Original concentration of soap solution before mixing the sol.	Calculated concentration of soap in the mixed solution before adsorption.	Drop number of the mixture of sol and soap solution.	Observed concentration of soap in the mixed solution after adsorption	Amount of soap adsorbed per 100 C.C. of the sol.
0.5000%	0.2500%	624	0.2000%	0.100 gms.
0.3750%	0.1875%	619	0.1438%	0.087 "
0.2500%	0.1250%	608	0.0875%	0.075 "
0.1250%	0.0625%	544	0.0563%	0.012 "

Some experiments were then performed with solid adsorbents. The fine precipitates employed were Merck's pure Zinc Oxide, Manganese Dioxide, Alumina, Red Lead, Fuller's earth, Barium Carbonate and Lead Chloride.

The particles of uniform sizes were separated by passing them through sieves of meshes of two successive

sizes (40 and 60 per inch). 50 C. C. of soap solutions of various concentrations were added to 5 grams of the precipitate and the mixtures were left for 24 hours. The soap solutions were then filtered and their concentrations were determined as described before by counting the number of drops in the given volume of the filtrate. To avoid any adsorption by filter papers during filtration, specially prepared filter papers were used. They were first soaked in soap solution of the same strength as added to the precipitates and were then dried after thorough washing. The results with various precipitates are shown in the following tables :—

TABLE VI.

Soap used = Sodium oleate.
Solid adsorbent used = Zinc Oxide.

Quantity of the solid. (m)	Original concentration of soap solution before mixing zinc oxide.	Drop number of the supernatant liquid.	Observed concentration of soap solution after adsorption. (c)	Amount of soap adsorbed by the solid. (s)	x/m
5 gm.	0.5000%	481	0.0469%	0.2265 gms.	0.0453
5 "	0.3750%	381	0.0250%	0.1750 "	0.0350
5 "	0.2500%	272	0.0063%	0.1218 "	0.0244
5 "	0.1250%	240	0.0000%	0.0625 "	0.0125

TABLE VII.

Soap used = Sodium oleate.
Solid adsorbent used = Manganese dioxide.

Quantity of the solid. (m)	Original concentration of soap solution before mixing manganese dioxide.	Drop number of the supernatant liquid.	Observed concentration of soap solution after adsorption. (c)	Amount of soap adsorbed by the solid. (s)	x/m
5 gms.	0.5000%	582	0.0656%	0.2172 gms.	0.0484
5 "	0.3750%	508	0.0500%	0.1625 "	0.0325
5 "	0.2500%	410	0.0312%	0.1094 "	0.0219
5 "	0.1250%	270	0.0064%	0.0593 "	0.0119

TABLE VIII.

Soap used = Sodium oleate.
Solid adsorbent used = Alumina.

Quantity of the solid. (n.)	Original concentration of soap solution before mixing Alumina.	Drop number of the supernatant liquid.	Observed concentration of soap solution after adsorption. (c)	Amount of soap adsorbed by the solid. (s)	x/m
5 gms.	0.5000%	620	0.1562%	0.1719 gms.	0.0344
5 "	0.3750%	596	0.0687%	0.1531 "	0.0306
5 "	0.2500%	555	0.0593%	0.0968 "	0.0191
5 "	0.1250%	340	0.0187%	0.0681 "	0.0106

TABLE IX.

Soap used = Sodium oleate.
Solid adsorbent used = Red Lead.

Quantity of the solid. (m)	Original concentration of soap solution before mixing Red lead.	Drop number of the supernatant liquid.	Observed concentration of soap solution after adsorption. (c)	Amount of soap adsorbed by the solid. (s)	x/m
5 gms.	0.5000%	578	0.0625%	0.2188 gms.	0.0488
5 "	0.3750%	578	0.0625%	0.1532 "	0.0312
5 "	0.2500%	578	0.0625%	0.0937 "	0.0187
5 "	0.1250%	550	0.0593	0.0620 "	0.0084

TABLE X.

Soap used = Sodium oleate.
Solid adsorbent used = Fuller's earth.

Quantity of the solid. (m)	Original concentration of soap solution before mixing Fuller's earth.	Drop number of the supernatant liquid.	Observed concentration of soap solution after adsorption. (c)	Amount of soap adsorbed by the solid. (s)	x/m
2 gms.	0.5000%	624	0.2000%	0.0150 gms.	0.0750
2 "	0.3750%	610	0.0875%	0.1437 "	0.0718
2 "	0.2500%	572	0.0625%	0.0937 "	0.0468
2 "	0.1250%	432	0.0375%	0.0437 "	0.0218

TABLE XI.

Soap used = Sodium oleate.
Solid adsorbent used = Barium Carbonate.

Quantity of the solid. (m)	Original concentration of soap solution before mixing carbonate	Drop number of the supernatant liquid.	Observed concentration of soap solution after adsorption. (c)	Amount of soap adsorbed by the solid. (s)	x/m
5 gms.	0.5000%	600	0.0719%	0.2140 gms.	0.0480
5 "	0.3750%	592	0.0688%	0.1531 "	0.0306
5 "	0.2500%	584	0.0656%	0.0922 "	0.0184
5 "	0.1250%	540	0.0562%	0.0344 "	0.0069

TABLE XII.

Soap used = Sodium oleate.
Adsorbent used = Lead Chloride.

Quantity of the solid. (m)	Original concentration of soap solution before mixing lead chloride.	Drop number of the supernatant liquid.	Observed concentration of soap solution after adsorption. (c)	Amount of soap adsorbed by the solid. (s)	x/m
5 gms.	0.5000%	250	0.0031%	0.2484 gms.	0.0497
5 "	0.3750%	246	0.0011%	0.1867 "	0.0373
5 "	0.2500%	242	0.0008%	0.1246 "	0.0249
5 "	0.1250%	240	0.0000%	0.0625 "	0.0125

It will be seen from tables III-V that the observed concentration of the soap is not half as is expected on mixture law but is in all cases less. The diminution in concentration is due to the adsorption of soap molecules by the particles of colloidal solutions which offer such a large surface (*cf.* Gibbs-Thomson equation). The same

conclusion can be drawn from the experiments made on fine powders. Also in each case the value of x/m have been calculated and the results indicate that the value of x/m decreases as the concentration of the soap is decreased. These observations clearly show that the phenomenon of protection is related to adsorption and precedes either an increase in the density of charge on the colloid particles or the formation of an envelope round them.

In order to see whether Freundlich's equation is applicable to these cases of adsorption, graphs with x/m and C , the end concentration, as co-ordinates were drawn. It was found that only in a few cases the $\log x/m$ and $\log C$ curves were straight lines (*cf.* Prasad, Shrivastava and Gupta, "The mechanism of adsorption by colloidal solution and precipitate" communicated to *Kolloid Zeitschrift*).

The state of the adsorbed soap was then examined by performing the following experiments:—

In the case of soap and sol system, the colloidal solution was coagulated by N/10 Barium Chloride and the coagula was well washed on the filter paper to remove the precipitating agent and the mechanically adhering soap molecules. As Whitney and Ober have shown (*Journ. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 23, 342, 1901), the above process does not remove any adsorbed substance. The coagula was then boiled in water for a long time and the numbers of the water so obtained were determined. Similarly fine powders were first well washed to remove any adhering soap molecules and then boiled in water for sufficient time. The drop numbers of this water were then counted as before. The results of only two cases are given in Tables XIII and XIV. Results obtained in case of other sols and precipitates were of the same nature.

TABLE XIII.

Soap used - =Sodium oleate.
 Colloidal substance used =Arsenic hydrosulphide sol
 containing 0.8530 gram
 of As_2S_3 per litre.

Original concentration of soap solution before mixing the sol	Calculated concentration of soap in the mixed solution before adsorption.	Drop number of the mixture of sol and soap solution.	Observed concentration of soap in the mixed solution after adsorption. (c)	Amount of soap adsorbed per 100 C.C. of the sol. (a)	Drop number of the washings.
0.500%	0.2500%	595	0.0688 gms.	0.3624 gms.	240
0.375%	0.1875%	518	0.0500 "	0.2750 "	240
0.250%	0.1250%	371	0.0250 "	0.2000 "	240
0.125%	0.0625%	268	0.0083 "	0.1125 "	240

TABLE XIV.

Soap used =Sodium oleate.
 Solid adsorbent used =Zinc oxide.

Quantity of the solid. (m)	Original concentration of soap solution before mixing Zinc oxide.	Drop number of the supernatant liquid	Observed concentration of soap solution after adsorption. (c)	Amount of soap adsorbed by the solid. (a)	Drop number of the washings.
5 gms.	0.500%	491	0.0469%	0.2265 gms.	240
5 "	0.375%	381	0.2500%	0.1750 "	240
5 "	0.250%	272	0.0083%	0.1218 "	240
5 "	0.125%	240	0.0000%	0.0625 "	240

The above observations clearly show that the adsorbed soap has lost its well known property of dissolving in water and lowering the surface tension and thus amply support the chemical theory of adsorption.

Further qualitative experiments were made to see the presence of the constituents of soap in the coagula and the precipitates.

The washed precipitate or coagulum was first dried in an air oven. It was then mixed with copper oxide and heated in a test-tube. The gas evolved was passed in lime water which became milky. A control experiment was done side by side with copper oxide and zinc oxide or any other precipitate. No milkyness of lime water was observed in any of the latter cases. These experiments show that the constituents of soaps are present in the precipitates and the coagula but do not exhibit their ordinary property of solution in water as they have undergone a radical change in the adsorbed state.

Some experiments were then made to study the adsorption of dyes by the fine precipitates. The method employed for the above investigation was the ordinary colorimetric method. The results of these experiments were also in the same direction as that of the soap solutions. The dye is adsorbed by the precipitates and loses its property of solubility in water in the adsorbed state.

These results clearly point out the advantage of using mordants in making a dye fast on a cloth. The mordants adsorb the dyes which in the adsorbed state undergo a vast change in the physical properties. They lose the property of solution in water in the adsorbed state and consequently the cloth remains unaffected by repeated washings.

UNIVERSITY CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
PUNJAB UNIVERSITY,
LAHORE.

[*Received March 30, 1925.*]
